

Skills 4 eOSC

D7.4 Guidelines for sustainability of the network of Competence Centres

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable provides an analysis of the adapted business model for project outcomes, sustainability prospects of the Skills4EOSC Competence Centres. It also outlines, the actions undertaken to ensure sustainability of the project outcomes. The Competence Centre Network has been considered as an owner of both tangible outputs as well as community impacts and outcomes after the end of the project. This has been confirmed by the members of the CC Network during the first General Assembly meeting. The report provides the roadmap to ensure short-to-mid-term sustainability, with the outlook towards long-term viability and evolution.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Full term</i>
CC	Competence Centre
CC Network	Competence Centre Network
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MVS	Minimum Viable Skill Set
LMS	Learning Management System
OA5	Opportunity Area 5 (Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition, and Upskilling)
PU	Public (EU deliverable dissemination level)
QA	Quality Assurance
RDM	Research Data Management
INFRA	Horizon Europe Research Infrastructures programme

TERMINOLOGY

<i>Terminology/Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>
CC (Competence Centre)	A national, regional, institutional, or thematic hub within Skills4EOSC that coordinates, delivers training, and supports Open Science and FAIR practices in its region.
CC Network	The pan-European network of Competence Centres established by Skills4EOSC to enable coordinated training, knowledge sharing, and community building.
EOSC (European Open Science Cloud)	A European initiative to create a federated infrastructure enabling access to FAIR data and services for research across borders and disciplines.
EOSC Portal	The central gateway to EOSC services, resources, and information, including the EOSC Marketplace, training materials, and policy documents.
FAIR Principles	Guidelines ensuring that research data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.
FAIR-by-design methodology	A methodology developed in Skills4EOSC to embed FAIR principles directly into research workflows, training, and infrastructure from the start.
MVS (Minimum Viable Skill Set)	A defined set of essential Open Science skills tailored to specific professional roles, created in Skills4EOSC.
OA5 (Opportunity Area 5)	One of the five strategic priority areas in the EOSC Association, focusing on Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition, and Upskilling.
EOSC Federation	The federated structure of national and thematic nodes and service providers that collectively deliver the EOSC vision.
EOSC Federation Handbook	A reference document outlining the governance, roles, and operational principles of the EOSC Federation.
LMS (Learning Management System)	A digital platform used to deliver, manage, and track training activities in Skills4EOSC.
User Support Network	A distributed network within Skills4EOSC providing technical and service-related support to users, often

	including helpdesk-as-a-service models.
Data Professional Network	A community of researchers and data professionals who share expertise, best practices, and collaborate on data management, stewardship, and Open Science principles.
Horizon Europe INFRA programme	An EU funding programme supporting research infrastructure, including calls relevant to EOSC skills, training, and nodes.
QA (Quality Assurance)	Processes and standards designed to ensure the quality, consistency, and compliance of training, outputs, and methodologies.

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1 Executive summary

Deliverable D7.4 reports activities of task 7.5 aiming to ensure the uptake of project results after the end of the Skills4EOSC project. The report is based on the analysis of sustainability provided in the MS7.5 milestone report [R1], as well as the elaborated organisational outline of the Competence Centre Network provided in the deliverable D7.3 [R2]. Activities to ensure the sustainability of project outputs and project impact will continue beyond the point of writing of this report as well. This report represents the situation as it is at the time of writing and provides the guidance for further actions.

This report outlines further progress of actions that were initially included in the proposed roadmap of [R1]. It presents the assessment of the value proposition and adapted business model canvas for the groups of results of the project and Competence Centre Network. Analysis proves that the CC Network is the right vehicle to ensure the viability and evolution of project results. Furthermore, the report includes results of the survey evaluating the potential sustainability of the Competence Centre Network. The survey indicates that – although not without some challenges – Competence Centres demonstrate good to moderate prospects of sustainability, therefore providing additional substantiation of the Network as an appropriate choice as owner of the project legacy after the end of the project.

A number of actions were undertaken between the submission of the MS7.5 milestone report [R1], and submission of this deliverable. Updated list of the first steps identified in [R1] is presented in Table 3.

Most notably: the Competence Centre workshop was conducted to discuss the value and priorities of sustainability actions, and the first General Assembly of the Competence Centre Network was held, where the first presidency of the Network was assigned in accordance with the governance guidance of CC Network provided in [R2]. This report incorporates directions outlined during these events into the proposed roadmap, outlining main actions for three years after the end of the project (until Sep 2028). The roadmap does not prescribe the exact date at which actions have to be undertaken; it defines 4 checkpoints within the 3-year span, that would allow the Competence Centre Network to evaluate the progress.

While task 7.5 provided the basic direction and outline, this report summarises the project-wide effort to ensure the sustainability of results, most notably

complemented by representatives of the Competence Centres. The actions reported in this deliverable will ensure at least the short-to-mid term sustainability of project outcomes.

2 Introduction and scope

This report presents an analysis of the value and viability options of the Skills4EOSC project outcomes, and provides a final roadmap for their sustainability. Roadmap has been derived from the outcome of business model analysis and consists of actions and decisions undertaken by the project consortium. It also outlines potential actions and decisions for the community after the end of the project.

This report has to be considered together with the Report of Milestone MS 7.5 "Analysis of Sustainability" [R1] and the Deliverable D7.3 "Report on Competence Centres and user support networks and recommendations for networks evolution" [R2]. The description of methodology for the modified business model analysis is described in [R1], while the organisational setup and parts of the roadmap were derived from [R2]. These documents thus constitute an integral contribution to the sustainability of project outcomes.

The identified criteria for sustainability of a project outcome are:

- Owner of an outcome;
- Procedures for the evolution;
- Necessary resources to ensure continuous availability.

These criteria also discussed in [R1] in greater detail. Here we demonstrate that the approach to sustainability will meet the outlined criteria. The analysis of the value and business model for sustainability is concluded based on the groups of project outcomes.

2.1 Summary of Skills4EOSC Project Outcomes

The Skills4EOSC project has delivered a wide range of outputs that together support the development of Open Science skills and infrastructure across Europe. These outputs span training materials, methodologies, reports, and community structures such as the Competence Centre Network and the User Support Network.

The outcomes and impact of the project are not limited to tangible outputs. The project has ensured advocacy, representation, and organisation of the community, advancing the the standardisation of Open Science skills throughout Europe.

Taking into account the overall impact of the project, we propose grouping the outcomes into three main categories for further analysis:

1. **Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Network, Knowledge Dissemination, Advocacy, Monitoring, and Network Expansion.** These outcomes include the outward-facing activities of promoting Open Science and EOSC Skills as well as inward-facing organisational efforts to ensure value to the Skills4EOSC Competence Centres via the CC Network. These activities are summarised in other project reports, including [R2].
2. **Training, Upskilling, Quality Assurance, and Community Standards.** This group of outputs contains training materials, curricula, learning paths complemented with the pilot training sessions. The group also contains appropriate methodologies and proposed community standards like certification, the recognition framework, and the FAIR-by-design methodology, as well as guides, e.g., feedback evaluation guide. Trainings and community standards are outlined in appropriate reports and deliverables. This group of outcomes also includes the toolkit for training, including Learning Management System supporting training process.
3. **User Support Network and Other Professional Networks.** This group refers to the organisation effort for the User Support Network as well as toolkits and guidelines to kick-start and organise other professional networks. Brief description of the outputs of the project and their grouping.

Table 1 provides an overview of the key tangible output types produced during the project, along with their quantity and descriptions. This table is intended to give a concise, overview of the tangible results achieved to date.

Table 1 Summary of outputs of Skills4EOSC project

Output Type	Number Produced	Examples / Notes
MVS profiles	14	Profiles defining Minimum Viable Skill Sets for roles such as Data Steward, FAIR Champion, Research Software Engineer.
Trainings	34	Live online sessions, in-person workshops, self-paced online modules aligned with FAIR and Open Science standards.

Methodologies	11	FAIR-by-Design methodology, certification frameworks, starter kits for professional networks.
Reports	9	Including Deliverable D7.4 (this report) and milestone and deliverable documents on sustainability, training, and network development.
Competence Centre Network	1	Pan-European network connecting national, regional, and thematic Competence Centres to share knowledge and coordinate activities.
User Support & Professionals Networks	12	Distributed support model including helpdesk-as-a-service approaches and professional networking for data experts and data stewards.

Note: Numbers are based on the outputs available at the time of writing and may be further expanded before the project’s conclusion. Please refer to the Skills4EOSC community in Zenodo for the most up-to-date information (<https://zenodo.org/communities/skills4eosc/>).

The launch of the new call HORIZON-INFRA-2025-01-EOSC-04 ‘Data stewards, skills and training for Open Science and FAIR practices¹’, with a deadline on 18 September 2025, represents a key opportunity to ensure the sustainability of the outcomes and structures developed within the Skills4EOSC project. The call explicitly acknowledges the value of Skills4EOSC’s work and encourages future projects to build upon its results, particularly in developing consistent data steward curricula, strengthening European competence networks, and fostering the uptake of FAIR and Open Science practices. Skills4EOSC outcomes will be further consolidated and expanded through this new European Commission initiative.

¹ See at <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/HORIZON-INFRA-2025-01-EOSC-04?order=DESC&pageNumber=1&pageSize=50&sortBy=relevance&keywords=HORIZON-INFRA-2025-01-EOSC-04:%20Data%20stewards,%20skills%20and%20training%20for%20Open%20Science%20and%20FAIR%20practices&isExactMatch=true&status=31094501,31094502,31094503&frameworkProgramme=43108390>

3 Adapted business model canvas

In this chapter, we present the adapted Business Model Canvas (BMC), tailored for analysing value networks within the Skills4EOSC project. The BMC structure is based on the methodology in [R6], which we have modified to reflect the collaborative, non-commercial, and community-driven nature of the Skills4EOSC Competence Centres Network and its associated professional and user support networks. The transformation from the classical BMC approach is outlined in the Figure 1. Our adaptation emphasises value co-creation, knowledge dissemination, advocacy, training standardisation, and sustained community engagement. The canvas categories have been adjusted to align with the three outcome groups identified in the Methodology section of the milestone report (1) the Competence Centre Network, (2) training and upskilling services, and (3) user support and professional networks.

This ensures that the BMC reflects both the operational structure and the strategic objectives of the Skills4EOSC network while providing a practical framework for assessing sustainability factors such as governance, technical infrastructure, and policy alignment.

The Business Model Canvas-Value Network

Original Work: "Business Model Canvas" by Strategyzer AG, available at www.strategyzer.com, licensed under CC BY-SA 3.0.
 Adaptation: This version has been adapted for a value network, and any further adaptations or redistribution must be shared under the same Creative Commons license.

Figure 1. Business model canvas value network

3.1 Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Network, Knowledge Dissemination, Advocacy, Monitoring, and Network Expansion

This section focuses on the creation, coordination, and growth of the S4E Competence Centres Network. The primary value of this group of project outcomes is building long-term capacity for Open Science, advocating for EOSC principles, and ensuring strategic alignment among national and thematic Competence Centres. Activities include community engagement, knowledge exchange, policy advocacy, and monitoring the evolving needs of stakeholders. Examples include workshops with national Competence Centres, sharing training resources, contributions to the OA5 expert group, and annual surveys. Partnerships span national Competence Centres, thematic groups, and policy bodies, e.g., OSCARS, European Civil Protection Forum, etc.. Engagement channels include community platforms, the EOSC EU Node, and high-level events. Sustainability is planned through EU funding, national support, and advisory services.

From the general BMC structure, the following elements have been customised to reflect the specific role and objectives of the Competence Centre Network: Value Propositions, Key Activities, Key Partners and Customer Segments (as seen in Figure 2). These components have been adapted to emphasise network creation, Open Science advocacy, stakeholder engagement, and sustainable support mechanisms within the Skills4EOSC ecosystem.

Figure 2 CC Network Value propositions and other subcomponents

3.2 Training, Upskilling, Quality Assurance, and Community Standards

This section highlights the delivery of harmonised, FAIR-compliant training materials and services. It aims to ensure researchers, students, and support staff can access certified, high-quality, and EOSC-aligned training. Key activities include developing training curricula, delivering sessions, tracking competences, and issuing certifications. Examples include creating FAIR-by-design learning paths, running live online pilot training sessions, monitoring learner progress via the Skills4EOSC LMS, and awarding CC-endorsed course certificates. Resources and agents like expert trainers, infrastructure, and metadata-rich content are essential. Training is delivered via catalogues and digital platforms. Costs to consider should cover platform maintenance, trainer time, and certification frameworks.

Figure 3 Training Value propositions and other subcomponents

From the general BMC structure, the following elements have been customised to reflect the specific priorities of the Training, Upskilling, and Community Standards group: Value Propositions, Key Activities, Key Resources and Customer Segments (as seen in Figure 3). These components have been tailored to emphasise the delivery of certified, FAIR-compliant training services, the development of competence frameworks, and the provision of sustainable, high-quality learning pathways for EOSC-related communities.

3.3 User Support Network and Other Professional Networks

This section covers the establishment of User Support Network and Data professional networks as output from the project. The User Support Network includes technical teams or groups of people that support their own users with the services they offer, such as helpdesk-as-a-service models for research infrastructures, incident and request management, community

knowledge sharing, and co-creation of support solutions. Examples include incident and request management for research infrastructures, best practice exchange sessions, and joint troubleshooting for FAIR data implementation.

The Data Stewards Networks consists of researchers and other data professionals who collaborate to share expertise, develop best practices, and foster a community of practice around data management, stewardship, and open science principles.

From the general BMC structure, the following elements have been customised to capture the specific role and services of the User Support Network and related professional networks: Value Propositions, Key Activities, Customer Relationships and Customer Segments (as seen in Figure 4). These elements have been adapted to reflect the emphasis on tailored, federated support services, collaborative knowledge sharing, and the development of distributed helpdesk models to meet the operational and community needs within the EOsc ecosystem.

Figure 4 User Support Network Value propositions and other subcomponents

4 Analysis of sustainability of project outcomes

Evaluation of sustainability requires confirmation of the analysis through observation. We conducted a brief survey [R4] of Competence Centres participating in the Skills4EOSC CC Network.

The survey questions were structured based on the key components of the adapted Business Model Canvas for value networks, ensuring alignment with the value propositions, key activities, partnerships, resources, stakeholder relationships, and sustainability mechanisms identified in the framework.

The purpose of the survey was to confirm the results of analysis and identify major challenges for Competence Centres in order to derive the agenda for future workshops. Questions were grouped by the group of outcomes of the Skills4EOSC project, the questions themselves were constructed in a way to provide the engagement of Competence Centres and value of each group of outcomes. Moreover, cross-cutting questions were introduced to identify major challenges motivation of Competence Centres. Answers to the questionnaire could also be used to prove the sustainability prospects of each Competence Centre.

The questionnaire was sent to all the Competence Centres involved in the Competence Centre Network and recorded in [R2]. Nine responses were received. Additionally, the roadmap to sustainability was presented to Competence Centres during the workshop on 28 May 2025. Representatives of each Competence Centre then were asked to voice their position (see Appendix 3 for more information on relevant events).

4.1 Survey method and data collection

4.1.1 Methodology

The survey employed a structured questionnaire approach, utilising both multiple-choice and open-ended questions to capture quantitative metrics and qualitative insights. The questionnaire comprised four parts:

- 1st group of questions assessing potential impact of Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Network, Knowledge Dissemination, Advocacy, Monitoring, and Network Expansion;
- 2nd group of questions assessing potential impact of Training, Upskilling, Quality Assurance, and Community Standards;
- 3rd group of questions assessing potential impact of User Support Network and Other Professional Networks
- Cross-cutting questions for the better understanding of situations of individual Competence Centres:
 - How do you plan to sustain your CC activities after the project ends? What funding models are you exploring?
 - What would you say is your most impactful contribution to Skills4EOSC so far?
 - What would you say is your most impactful contribution to Skills4EOSC so far?
 - What support or collaboration would you like from the broader network?

The full template is provided in the [R4].

4.1.2 Data Collection Process

Data collection was conducted using a structured Excel-based questionnaire with well-defined multiple-choice response options. This approach ensured consistent and easily analysable data capture across all participating Competence Centres, and clear instructions were provided to maximise participation and maintain high data quality.

4.1.3 Participant Profile

The survey targeted all active Competence Centres within the Skills4EOSC network, representing diverse geographical regions, institutional types, and domain specialisation. This approach ensures the findings reflect the full spectrum of Competence Centre activities and perspectives within the network.

4.2 Evaluation of potential impact of project outcome groups

In this section, we report all our findings from the analysis of the impact of Skills4EOSC outcomes.

Figure 5 illustrates how Competence Centres (CCs) participate in the Skills4EOSC network, including their engagement with national and EU-level stakeholders and the conditions needed to enhance their outreach, based on answers to the 1st group of questions. Most respondents reported playing a coordination (8) and community-building (6) role in the network. Engagement is higher at the national (9) than the EU level (6). Key factors for expanding outreach include support for collaborative activities (8), funding (5), and opportunities for expertise exchange (5).

Figure 5 Responses from Group 1 (CCs involved in Network, Knowledge Dissemination, and Advocacy) on their roles, stakeholder engagement, and needs for expanding outreach within the Skills4EOSC CC Network

Figure 6 presents how Competence Centres are contributing to training activities relevant to the Skills4EOSC network based on answers to the 2nd group of questions. The most commonly delivered training formats are live

online sessions (9), in-person training (8), and self-paced online modules (6). While quality assurance practices vary, 3 CCs align with EOSC/Skills4EOSC guidelines, and 2 offer certified programs. On training standards, 6 CCs actively promote standards, 1 is involved in development, and 1 is interested in future participation. This highlights a strong commitment to both quality and harmonisation of training practices.

Figure 6 Responses from Group 2 (CCs focused on Training, Upskilling, Quality Assurance, and Standards) regarding training formats, quality assurance practices, and involvement in training standards within the Skills4EOSC CCs network

Figure 7 illustrates how Competence Centres engage in user support and professional networking activities based on answers to the 3rd group of questions. Most respondents are connected to networks such as the EOSC Association (7), EOSC Future (2), and EuroCC (2), while others operate or plan to integrate helpdesk services at national (2) or EU (1) levels. Common user requests include training/resource needs (7), technical issues (5), and FAIR/data management guidance (5). The data reveals active involvement in support infrastructure and growing connections to broader data professional communities.

Figure 7 Responses from Group 3 (CCs focused on User Support and Data Professional Networks) on helpdesk integration, user support needs, and connections to data professional networks within the Skills4EOSC network

To complement the figures presented above, Table 2 below summarises the main findings from the survey for each of the three groups. This format provides a clear overview of activities, practices, strengths, and gaps without the need for detailed country-by-country comparison. It is intended as a concise reference point for the sustainability evaluation in section 4.3.

Table 2 Summary of survey results for each Skills4EOSC outcome group

Group outcomes	of	Main activities	Most common practices/Fo rmats	Notable strengths	Key Needs/Gaps
Group 1: CC Network, Knowledge Dissemination, Advocacy		Coordination of national and thematic CCs; community building; policy engagement	Engagement mainly at national level; regular meetings and knowledge exchange	Strong national coordination roles; active community building	Increased EU-level engagement; more support for collaborative activities and expertise exchange; funding stability
Group 2: Training, Upskilling, QA, Standards		Development and delivery of training; competence tracking; certification	Live online training (most common), in-person training, self-paced modules	Promotion of standards; some certified programmes; diverse formats	Greater harmonisation of QA practices; wider adoption of certification frameworks
Group 3: User Support & Professional Networks		Helpdesk models; technical support; best practice exchange	Connections to EOSC Association, EOSC Future, EuroCC; user request handling	Addressing training/resource requests and FAIR/data management queries	Broader integration with EU-level helpdesks; expansion of professional networks

Overall, the survey findings underline the varied but complementary roles Competence Centres have across the Skills4EOSC network, from coordination and training through to user support and promotion of standards, showing active involvement across core areas of Open Science capacity development. The summary table above captures these findings at a glance. Further questions on specific sustainability actions and longer-term impact are covered in the following chapter.

4.3 Sustainability evaluation methodology and dimensions

4.3.1 Methodology Evaluation Framework

The four cross-cutting questions were analysed, interpreted, and systematically mapped to the evaluation dimensions based on their primary focus and relevance to the sustainability assessment criteria. This evaluation is an attempt to extrapolate the sustainability of individual Competence Centres as a part of the CC Network (see Dimension 3) based solely on answers provided to the questionnaire, in order to identify the trends. The criteria for assigning values to each parameters were based on the expert knowledge of the task team.

A four-dimensional system was developed to evaluate CC sustainability across critical operational areas:

- Financial sustainability;
- Organisational capacity;
- Skills4EOSC network engagement and impact
- Strategic alignment and long-time future readiness

This approach draws on established qualitative sustainability assessment methodologies, particularly the Program Sustainability Assessment Tool (PSAT) framework developed by Luke et al. (2014) [R7], which provides a validated approach to measuring program capacity for sustainability through multi-dimensional qualitative assessment rather than purely quantitative metrics.

The overall assessment of sustainability of Competence Centres is derived from evaluation of answers along proposed dimensions taking account of inter-relations between dimensions.

4.3.2 Evaluation of sustainability by each dimension

1. Financial Sustainability

This dimension represents a critical determinant of long-term viability. The evaluation examines funding strategies ranging from secured multi-year institutional/national and project funding to limited or unclear funding approaches. Assessment considers funding source diversity, duration of commitments, and institutional backing.

The column graph in Figure 8 summarises keywords extracted from the textual responses received from various countries, categorised by response type (e.g., "Follow-up," "In kind," "Institution," etc.). Each CC contributed one or more responses across different categories, with notable participation in "Projects" and "In kind" contributions.

Figure 8 Distribution of keywords for the financial sustainability

2. Organisational Capacity

Evaluates the structural and staffing capabilities of each CC. The assessment examines organisational models ranging from distributed network structures with extensive institutional participation to minimal or developing organisational frameworks. Key factors include staffing adequacy, institutional support, and operational resilience.

Figure 9 displays the main challenges currently faced by CCs across participating countries. Staffing limitations were the most frequently cited obstacle, followed by issues with Funding, Coordination, and Engagement. Countries such as France and Italy identified multiple barriers, highlighting complex implementation environments. While a few Centres reported challenges related to Policies, Training, and Guidelines, e.g. lack of discipline-specific materials and training, only one country (Czech Republic) reported no major obstacles. The results indicate that operational and human resource constraints remain the most pressing issues within the network.

Figure 9 Major challenges faced by national Competence Centres in the Skills4EOsc network

3. Skills4EOSC Network Engagement & Impact

Measures active contributions to the Skills4EOSC network and the broader Open Science community. Scoring spans from multiple significant contributions across curricula, training, and networking to minimal or unclear contributions. Assessment includes participation in deliverables, knowledge sharing, and community building activities.

Figure 10 Most impactful contributions by national Competence Centres to the Skills4EOSC initiative

This column graph in Figure 10 summarises the most impactful contributions identified by CCs across different countries within the Skills4EOSC network. Contributions vary widely, with frequent mentions of Training, Community building, and Networking. Notable country-specific highlights include Germany’s role in Certification, Finland and Sweden’s emphasis on Curricula and Training, and North Macedonia’s involvement in Community and the FBDM (Fair-by Design Methodology). The diversity of responses underscores the multidimensional impact of national efforts within the broader Skills4EOSC framework.

4. Strategic Alignment & Long-term Future Readiness

Assesses long-term strategic planning and integration with national and international policies. The dimension evaluates awareness of challenges and opportunities, policy alignment, and future-oriented planning capabilities.

Figure 11 Types of support or collaboration desired by national Competence Centres from the broader Skills4EOOSC network

Figure 11 presents the types of support and collaboration that national CCs seek from the wider Skills4EOOSC network. The most frequently requested forms of support include collaboration on new projects, exchange of expertise, and access to external collaborations. Specific needs such as shared guidelines and trainer support were also mentioned by several countries. The responses emphasise a strong demand for more structured cooperation and knowledge sharing to enhance collective impact and operational capacity across the network.

4.3.3 Assessment of the overall sustainability

While each question primarily maps to one dimension, responses often provide insights across multiple dimensions as follows:

- Financial sustainability responses also inform organisational capacity when funding constraints staffing

- Obstacle identification reveals strategic planning gaps and network engagement barriers
- Impact contributions demonstrate organisational capacity and strategic alignment
- Collaboration requests reflect both network engagement maturity and organisational needs

The overall sustainability assessment of each Competence Centre as part of the CC Network integrates findings across all four key dimensions: Financial Sustainability, Organisational Capacity, Network Engagement, and Strategic Alignment. Rather than applying numerical weightings, this holistic evaluation considers the interconnected nature of these dimensions and their collective influence on long-term viability.

Highly Sustainable Centres (2 centres) demonstrate strong performance across multiple dimensions, showing comprehensive institutional backing, diverse funding sources, extensive network contributions, and clear strategic alignment. These centres exhibit balanced development with consistent approaches to sustainability challenges.

Moderately Sustainable Centres (7 centres) show solid foundations with varying strengths and development areas. This group displays mixed profiles - some excel in network engagement but face organisational challenges, while others maintain stable structures but require enhanced participation. Common characteristics include adequate baseline capacity with specific areas requiring strengthening.

It should be noted that this interpretation of results represents our analytical judgment based on the available data, and one-on-one interviews could be conducted to clarify and validate these findings.

4.4 Key gaps and conclusions

The sustainability assessment indicates that current members of the Competence Centre Network have good or moderate prospects to sustain themselves, and continue their contributions to the Network. The survey also indicates potential challenges that are indicated even by most well-

established Competence Centres. Funding stability and staffing limitations emerged as the most common challenges, directly affecting both organisational capacity and long-term strategic planning. Additionally, engagement at the EU level remains uneven, limiting broader policy alignment and opportunities for collaboration.

While most Competence Centres demonstrated strong involvement in training and community-building activities, variability in quality assurance practices and certified training provision indicates a need for greater harmonisation. The demand for structured collaboration mechanisms, expertise exchange, and joint project development points to a clear opportunity for strengthening network cohesion.

In conclusion, the assessment confirms that while several Competence Centres (notably France and Finland) exhibit high sustainability prospects, others face operational and strategic risks requiring targeted support. These findings will directly inform the agenda for future workshops and bilateral consultations to address gaps in funding, staffing, policy alignment, and network engagement.

5 Roadmap to sustainability

The initial roadmap for sustainability was included in [R1]. At the time of writing this report, a number of steps had been completed.

Table 3 Status update to the list of first steps towards sustainability

No	Description	Responsible	Status
1	Organisation structure of CCNetwork	Tasks 7.2 and 7.5	Completed. Organisation structure outlined in D7.3
2	Adoption of organisation structure	Task 7.2	Completed. Organisation structure adopted during the Paris workshop.
3	First meeting of the CCNetwork General Assembly	Tasks 7.2 and 7.5	Completed. 1 st GA meeting was held on 24-07-2025
4	Appointment of the first presidency	CC Network General Assembly	Completed. Presidency has been appointed during the 1 st GA meeting
5	Appointment of the editorial board	CC Network General Assembly	In progress, appointment scheduled for the 2 nd GA meeting in 2025.
6	Initial list of working groups	CC Network General Assembly	Pending.
7	Establishing infrastructure components and services	CC Network General Assembly	Completed. Initial proposal from GARR was presented during the 1 st GA meeting

8	<p>First independent meeting of CC Network General Assembly</p> <p>Verification of infrastructure resources and services</p> <p>Programme of future meetings and works.</p>	President of CC Network	Pending, scheduled to happen after the end of the project in 2025
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The roadmap proposed in this chapter concerns the sustained operation of CC Network after the end of the project. The proposal is based on the periodic checkpoints when a certain parameter can be measured, as compared to the milestones outlined in [R1].

The proposed roadmap draws upon the inputs obtained during a number of workshops and meetings with the Competence Centres (see Appendix 3 for more detail information), as well as on the results of questionnaire described in the previous chapter.

In accordance with inputs from Competence Centres during the Paris workshop, as provided in Appendix 1, the main priorities (challenges) to be addressed are:

1. Centralised funding (full or partial) of the CC Network activities;
2. Establishing work-groups and managing contributions by members;
3. Becoming part of EOSC EU Node;
4. Organising additional trainings.

The evaluation of project outputs by Competence Centres indicates that the most important outputs (in the order of importance) are:

1. Curricula and training materials;
2. FAIR-by-design methodology;
3. MVS profiles;
4. Methodologies and guides;
5. Communities;
6. Other outputs: (starter kits, infrastructure and tools, reports).

One of the key values of the CC Network is the pan-European dimension and representation of the European Competence Centres, as indicated in the documents from the Berlin workshop [R5] and business model analysis in Chapter 3. It is therefore strategically important to expand the network, including members primarily from EU and Associated countries.

5.1 Elaborated roadmap / implementation phase

We hereby propose that the evaluation of sustainability and viability of CC Network is performed on an annual basis after the end of the Skills4EOSC project. The first year after the end of the project will be essential to ensure the further sustainability of the CC Network. We therefore propose that first check of the viability be performed 6 months after the end of the project.

Competence Centres, or persons will have to be assigned responsibility by the General Assembly during the discussion of the roadmap.

We created an interactive timeline visualisation that displays the CC Network sustainability roadmap with all four checkpoints. The timeline features are displayed in Figure 12.

Figure 12 Skills4EOSC CC Network Sustainability Roadmap

Roadmap Checkpoints Overview

To ensure a structured and transparent follow-up after the conclusion of Skills4EOSC, the sustainability roadmap is organised around four checkpoints between 2026 and 2028. These checkpoints allow the Competence Centre Network to assess progress, address challenges, and make adjustments to its long-term strategy.

Check-point 1: March 2026

1. At least one meeting of the General Assembly has been organised after the end of the project.
2. All necessary resources have been migrated to the infrastructure provided by the CC Network or to open resources.
3. Editorial board and Working groups are approved.
4. Continuation of bi-monthly informal workshops for Competence Centres (members and candidates).
5. At least 1 Skills4EOSC training session has been replicated and conducted by Competence Centre; feedback was collected and processed.
6. Evaluation of EU funding opportunities for the CC Network must be completed.
7. A short and concise value proposition “what’s in it for me” should be prepared for potential members of the CC Network on the basis of <https://www.skills4eosc.eu/network/competence-centres/competence-centre-kit>.

Check-point 2: September 2026

1. Clear procedure of connecting to the EOSC EU Node has been established.
2. A representation in the EOSC Association Opportunity Area No. 5 and other relevant groups.
3. Evaluation of viability and evolution of project outputs is performed
4. At least 2 new members of the CC Network from EU countries
5. Provide concise information on which instrument and which call will be used to apply for funding to CC Network activities, and under which conditions.

6. At least 1 additional Skills4EOSC training session has been replicated and concluded by Competence Centre; feedback was collected and processed.
7. Report from the editorial board on the evolution of project outputs.

Check-point 3: September 2027

1. The funding situation is improved, or at least the proposal has been submitted for the CC Network activities
2. Evaluation of evolution of project outputs and their value.
3. Strategy of CC Network incorporating outputs from the Editorial Board and Working Groups
4. At least 2 new full members from EU countries
5. Evaluation of viability of members.

Check-point 4: September 2028

1. Decision on the value and future of the CC Network, e.g., integration with the EOSC Node.
2. Review of evolution and value of project outputs
3. Additional MVS profiles and trainings (both train-the-trainer and national pilot trainings)
4. At least 2 new members from EU countries

5.2 The 1st meeting of CC Network General Assembly

The 1st meeting of the CC Network General Assembly (GA) constitutes a major milestone in establishing an independent vehicle to carry over the work of Skills4EOSC project. It is considered as one of the key achievements of the task 7.5. The establishment of CC Network also serves as an ultimate indicator of the importance and impact of the Skills4EOSC project, confirmed by willingness of Competence Centres to contribute to advancement of upskilling work started by the project partners. An extract from the minutes of the GA meeting are included in Appendix 2. We represent summary agenda and outcomes of the meeting.

5.2.1 Draft agenda of the GA meeting

General Assembly Meeting No 01

24-07-2025 10:00-12.00 CET

Video-conference link: <https://blue.meet.garr.it/rooms/sar-bwj-yd4-amw/join>

Location of documents:

<https://gbox.garr.it/garrbox/s/2pQV0rHPbBswQIT?path=%2F1st%20CCNet%20GA%20meeting%2024.07.2025>

Meeting Agenda

Description	Status	Reference(s)	Who	Mins	Start
Welcome and Approval of Agenda	Approval	GA01Agenda	RT	10	10:00
Interim chair of GA	Approval	-	RT		
Appointment of presiding Competence Centre	Approval	Slides	RT	15	10:10
Permanent chair of the GA	Approval	-	RT		
Governance rules for the CC Network	Information	Slides	ICDI	20	10:25
Infrastructure resources	Information	Slides	AC	20	10:45
Next steps and elaborated roadmap	Discussion	GA01Slides	RT	40	11:05
Dates of next meetings and meeting close	Approval	Slides	ICDI	15	11:45

5.2.2 Summary recommendations and outcomes of the meeting

General assembly members have indicated the requirement to analyse the roadmap and have additional discussion during the upcoming GA meetings. This is beyond the publishing date of this deliverable. The roadmap is presented in this document without the latest updates from the GA. GA minutes are available in Appendix 2

The GA members have:

1. Appointed the Italian Competence Centre ICDI the first presiding Competence Centre, and appointed the representative of ICDI as a chair of the GA.
2. Briefly discussed the proposals for governance procedures, without conclusive results, earmarking them for further consideration and updates during upcoming meetings.

3. Were informed on the vision of the presiding Competence Centre regarding the infrastructure resources with some further discussion required regarding implementation for the shared workplace.
4. The proposed roadmap was discussed. Members have accepted the proposal of check-points in general. Members have requested time for the consideration of the content of each point. A few initial recommendations are addressed in this deliverable.

5.3 Recommendations to Competence Centres

Several recommendations to Competence Centres and to the CC Network are described in Section 7 of Deliverable 7.3 [R2].

The following new recommendations emerged during the discussion at the General Assembly held on 24 July 2025:

- **Infrastructure and Collaborative Tools:** Competence Centres are strongly encouraged to evaluate and propose alternative collaborative workspace solutions that can provide more sophisticated access differentiation and document management capabilities than the current interim GARRbox solution. While GARR has committed to four years of infrastructure support, the network's long-term sustainability would benefit from diversified technical solutions that better serve complex working group requirements and governance body needs. CCs should consider contributing technical expertise or infrastructure resources to enhance the network's collaborative capabilities.
- **Working Group Engagement and Strategic Focus:** All CCs should actively participate in the working group proposal process by September 15th, submitting concrete concepts for task-based activities that align with network priorities. CCs are particularly encouraged to propose working groups that address EOSC node synergies and integration opportunities, recognizing the evolving landscape of European open science infrastructure and the need to avoid duplication with other EOSC initiatives.
- **Editorial Board Participation and Output Stewardship:** CCs should designate representatives for Editorial Board participation, recognizing

this as a core network function essential for maintaining the quality and relevance of Skills4EOOSC outputs. CCs with specific expertise in Minimum Viable Skill Sets, FAIR-by-Design methodology, or Science for Policy Kits should prioritise Editorial Board engagement to ensure these valuable resources continue evolving with community needs. The Board's potential exploration of publishing opportunities also presents possibilities for enhancing institutional visibility and academic recognition for participating CCs.

- **Co-creation methodology, quality assurance & outputs updates.** The Competence Centre Network adopts the co-creation methodology and the quality assurance framework developed in Skills4EOOSC. This approach, based on preparation, development, and adjustment phases, is used to update learning resources and ensure they meet real community needs. Further details on the quality assurance and certification framework can be found in [R3].
- **Network Expansion and Relationship Building:** CCs should actively identify and cultivate relationships with potential new network members within their national and regional contexts, particularly focusing on organisations from EU and associated countries that could contribute complementary expertise or geographic coverage. CCs are encouraged to leverage existing connections with EOOSC nodes and national research infrastructures to explore integration opportunities and avoid fragmentation of open science support efforts across Europe.
- **Checkpoint Responsibility and Accountability:** All CCs must carefully assess their capacity for taking responsibility for specific Checkpoint 1 activities by September's end, ensuring realistic commitments that can be sustained throughout the transition period. CCs should prioritise activities that align with their organisational strengths while considering collaborative opportunities that could distribute workload effectively across the network.
- **Financial Sustainability and Resource Planning:** Competence Centres should begin exploring potential funding opportunities and resource sharing arrangements that could support network activities

beyond the current in-kind contribution model. This includes investigating possibilities for joint funding applications, leveraging existing institutional resources for network benefit, and identifying synergies with other European initiatives that might provide financial or technical support. Competence Centres are encouraged to document and share successful fundraising strategies that could benefit the broader network community.

5.4 Ensuring long-term sustainability

Ensuring the sustainability of the Skills4EOSC Competence Centres requires a dynamic and flexible approach, particularly in relation to the evolving EOSC Federation. As EOSC enters its implementation phase, with 13 National Nodes selected in the build-up phase—the first phase of developing an operational EOSC Federation² — the relationship between Competence Centres and Nodes has become a central topic within the Skills4EOSC Network. A dedicated meeting in March 2025 gathered nearly 50 Competence Centre representatives to explore this evolving landscape. The discussion highlighted the need for Competence Centres to maintain dedicated spaces for collaboration, which may operate in parallel with EOSC Nodes, given the diversity of national contexts. In some countries, like Italy, Competence Centres already contribute directly to the governance and working groups of the national Node. Elsewhere, integration may take different forms or remain informal.

At the European level, Skills4EOSC has played a leading role in shaping the EOSC agenda through its active contribution to ‘Opportunity Area 5 (OA5) – Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition & Upskilling of the EOSC Association. OA5 is one of the five strategic areas identified to guide EOSC implementation. Skills4EOSC has not only participated, but has also guided key discussions and significantly influenced the direction and results of the OA5 expert group. Many project partners—such as Sara Di Giorgio and Emma Lazzeri from the Italian ICDI Competence Centre—are active contributors to OA5 and simultaneously involved in building National EOSC Nodes, ensuring

² See at <https://eosc.eu/eosc-about/building-the-eosc-federation/>

continuity between strategic planning and practical implementation. This coordination effort was further strengthened by participation in high-level events like the EOSC Winter Schools (2024 and 2025) and Commission-led coordination meetings.

A major achievement of this European-level engagement has been the recognition of Skills4EOSC and its Competence Centres in the 'EOSC Federation Handbook'³, positioning the CC Network as a key player in the long-term EOSC framework.

Looking ahead, the role of Competence Centres is expected to continue evolving, in close synergy with future Horizon Europe initiatives. Notably, two 2025 calls under the Horizon Europe INFRA programme are directly relevant:

- HORIZON-INFRA-2025-01-EOSC-04: Data stewards, skills and training for Open Science and FAIR practices, which aims to build on and reinforce the results of Skills4EOSC, and
- HORIZON-INFRA-2025-01-EOSC-01: EOSC Nodes with federating capabilities for the EOSC Federation, which is expected to support the development of new National EOSC Nodes.

These two calls explicitly encourage collaboration between selected projects, which makes the link between future Competence Centres and EOSC Nodes even more relevant. The collaboration model developed within Skills4EOSC offers a strong foundation to support this alignment.

Finally, by offering practical training in Open Science practices, Competence Centres empower researchers to engage effectively with services and infrastructures offered by EOSC Nodes. Continued coordination with expert groups like OA5, further development of training catalogues, and potentially an EOSC Academy, will help ensure that people remain at the centre of EOSC's growth, fostering a resilient, distributed, and sustainable European Open Science ecosystem.

³ See at <https://eosc.eu/eosc-about/building-the-eosc-federation/eosc-federation-handbook/>

6 Conclusions

This report demonstrates that the Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Network provides a strong and adaptable foundation for sustaining the project's outcomes and impact well beyond its formal end. The analyses conducted, supported by survey evidence and community consultations, confirm that the Network is the most suitable vehicle to safeguard and evolve the Skills4EOSC legacy. While challenges remain in areas such as funding stability, staffing capacity, and harmonisation of practices, the structured roadmap presented here, combined with the governance mechanisms already established, provides clear pathways for addressing these gaps. The Competence Centres have shown both willingness and capacity to continue their activities, ensuring that training materials, methodologies, and community structures developed in the project remain accessible, relevant, and actively used.

Looking forward, the Network's integration with European Open Science policies and its synergies with EOSC Nodes and Horizon Europe initiatives will be critical for its long-term viability. By capitalising on opportunities such as the upcoming INFRA calls and strengthening collaboration across countries and communities, the Competence Centre Network is well-positioned to reinforce Europe's leadership in Open Science skills development. Ultimately, the commitment of the Competence Centres and the roadmap's defined checkpoints create favourable conditions for continued growth, ensuring that Skills4EOSC outputs remain a living resource that supports the evolving needs of researchers, institutions, and policymakers.

7 References

No	Description/Link
R1	Tuminauskas R., Berberi L., Janik J., Bjerde K., Di Giorgio S., Paolini G., Prandoni C., Corleto A. Milestone report MS 7.5 Sustainability analysis https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15111345
R2	Corleto A., Di Giorgio S., Paolini G., Berberi L., Candela L., Costantini A., Gaido L., Green D., Janik J., Tuminauskas R., Whyte A., Lazzeri E., Prandoni C., Evangelinou B. Deliverable D7.3 Report on Competence Centres and User Support Networks and recommendations for networks evolution https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15262091
R3	Sánchez Moreno M., Green D., Filiposka S., Winandi A., Drązewski K. Deliverable D2.7 Community-endorsed quality assurance and certification framework for professional training and qualifications - final version (https://zenodo.org/records/15731878)
R4	Barberi L., Tuminauskas R. Template of questionnaire for the survey https://zenodo.org/records/16948310
R5	Results of the Berlin workshop of Competence Centres https://docs.google.com/document/d/1cfsim95-3zzH3kJArfUMbgG9Py4lhdsB_u2xtiRDH2Y
R6	Dara, M. Value networks and business models: formulating and demonstrating a methodology for the development of value networks and alignment of business models based on design science research methodology https://purl.utwente.nl/essays/63024
R7	Luke DA, Calhoun A, Robichaux CB, Elliott MB, Moreland-Russell S. The Program Sustainability Assessment Tool: a new instrument for public health programs. <i>Prev Chronic Dis.</i> 2014 Jan 23;11:130184. doi: 10.5888/pcd11.130184. PMID: 24456645; PMCID: PMC3900326.

Appendix 1: Results of the Paris workshop interactive session

Please provide the indication the value of the project outputs for your CC or organisation beyond the scope and duration of Skills4EOSC project.

1. What is the likelihood of your contribution to use and development of these outputs after the project (evaluate each with scale from 1 to 5):

37 respondents

d. Training materials

e. Certification framework

f. Methodologies and guides

g. Communities (CC Network, User support network)

h. Starter kits for professional networks

i. Tools and infrastructure (e.g. virtual learning environment)

j. Reports (e.g. sustainability report)

2. **What would be the most important next steps for CC Network after the end of Skills4EOSC project (evaluate each with scale from 1 to 5):**

32 respondents

a. Managing the contributions by members;

b. Organising additional trainings;

c. Establishing the schedule of monthly meetings (workshops)

d. Establishing the working groups to manage the evolution of project outputs;

e. Looking for sources of funding for CC Network activities;

f. Becoming part of EU EOSC Node;

g. Establishing own EOSC Node;

h. Other

Appendix 2: Extract from the minutes of the General Assembly

General Assembly Meeting Minutes

Skills4EOSC Competence Centres Network

First General Assembly Meeting

Date: 24 July 2025

Meeting Type: Online

Number of participants: 18 participants belonging to 11 different Countries / Competence Centres

Key Decisions and Outcomes

1. First Presiding Competence Center Appointment

The chair opened the meeting and proposed **ICDI (Italian Competence Center)** as the first presiding Competence Centre. ICDI's extensive background was presented, including their role as one of the four founding organisations of EOSC Association and their substantial achievements: over 170 active members in their Italian data steward network, 160 train-the-trainer participants (18% of European total), and the well-known "Open Science Café" series.

ICDI committed to providing infrastructure support (mailing lists, website, GARRbox) through in-kind contributions without requiring external funding. APPROVED by acclamation with no objections raised.

2. Infrastructure and Technical Foundation

GARR presented the technical infrastructure available for network operations. The system includes dual email lists (CC-network_GA for formal members, CC-network for all participants), Big Blue Button video conferencing, and a Moodle learning management system.

GARR committed to hosting and managing all tools for the next four years. The current Only Office collaborative platform will maintain document access but discontinue updates after December 2025, leading to the implementation of GARRbox as an interim collaborative solution with

password protection for GA members.

3. Governance Model

The project coordinator outlined the network's governance structure based on voluntary in-kind contributions with two membership levels: Letter of Intent (simple alignment expression) and Memorandum of Understanding (formal but non-binding agreement). The structure includes:

- **Editorial Board:** Critical component responsible for maintaining and updating Skills4EOSC outputs including Minimum Viable Skill Sets, FAIR-by-Design methodology, and training materials. Will operate as collaborative space rather than closed committee, with dedicated meeting planned for mid-October.
- **Working Groups:** Task-based teams for focused activities. Call for proposals launched via [EU Survey](#) with September 15th deadline. Suggested topics include network value proposition development, EOSC node synergies, and expansion strategies. Top 2-3 working groups will be selected through voting process.

4. Strategic Roadmap

The chair presented a checkpoint-based roadmap reflecting community priorities identified during the Paris workshop, particularly funding source identification and maintaining high-value curricular/training materials.

Checkpoint 1 (6 months post-project - March 2026): Essential transition activities including infrastructure migration, Editorial Board establishment, first working group approval, continued bi-monthly workshops, training session delivery, and "what's in it for me" value proposition development.

Checkpoint 2 (1 year post-project - September 2026): Strategic positioning including EOSC node integration exploration, project outputs viability evaluation, minimum two new EU/associated country members, and concrete funding acquisition plan development.

Checkpoint 3 (2 years post-project - September 2027): Clear funding proposal submission, continued outputs evaluation, and comprehensive network strategy development.

Checkpoint 4 (3 years post-project - September 2028): Network sustainability assessment, additional training materials development, and growth evaluation within and beyond EU.

5. Community Consensus

Round table feedback from all participating Competence Centres (CCs) revealed strong consensus supporting the proposed roadmap, governance structure, and infrastructure approach. Key concerns addressed included:

- **Geographic scope:** Modified from "European countries" to "EU and associated countries" following Tunisia's feedback, however it is important to attain the critical mass within the geographical scope of Horizon Europe and subsequent Framework programmes.
- **Working group coordination:** UK raised important concerns about potential duplication with other EOSC initiatives, emphasizing need for collaboration rather than competition.
- **Timeline flexibility:** Multiple CCs requested time until September for internal discussions about checkpoint responsibility assignments.
- **Trainings:** CCs have indicated the importance and value of the training materials, and willingness to continue delivering the Skills4EOSC trainings beyond the end of project. It will no longer be considered a pilot, contributing to training activities by Competence Centres.

All representatives expressed agreement with the roadmap feasibility while acknowledging the vacation period's impact on immediate detailed commitments.

Action Items and Timeline

September 2025:

- Working group proposals submission via EU Survey (deadline: September 15th)
- Competence Centre responsibility assignments for Checkpoint 1 activities (deadline: end of September)

October 2025:

- Editorial Board kick-off meeting (mid-October)
- Working group selection finalisation (October 15th)

- Next General Assembly meeting via Doodle poll (end of October)

November 2025:

- First Exchange Hour informal meeting (mid-November) - seeking volunteers to organise

Conclusion

The inaugural General Assembly successfully established the foundational governance structure and operational framework for sustainable network operation beyond the Skills4EOSC project completion. Strong community consensus, committed infrastructure support from GARR, and experienced leadership from ICDI create favorable conditions for network sustainability and growth.

The meeting demonstrated remarkable alignment among European CCs regarding strategic direction while maintaining flexibility for adaptation as the network evolves. The checkpoint system provides structured milestones while accommodating changing circumstances and community needs.

Appendix 3: Summary of relevant events

No	Event	Date	Description and relevance to sustainability
1	CC Network launch event	25 - 06 - 2024	<p>The event cemented the Competence Centre Network as an established organisational unit within the Skills4EOSC project.</p> <p>The event also was a start of more intensive collaboration between Competence Centres on relevant issues, including sustainability.</p> <p>The information about the event is available at https://www.skills4eosc.eu/participate/events/public-launch-of-the-skills4eosc-competence-centres-network</p>
2	Skills4EOSC Berlin workshop	21 - 09 - 2024	<p>Berlin workshop was co-located with the EOOSC Symposium 2024. It attracted wide participation from Skills4EOSC project as well as Competence Centres.</p> <p>Sustainability was one of the topics for the discussion for workshop participants. Results of this discussion have indicated the extent of willingness of Competence Centres to support outcomes of Skills4EOSC project after project end.</p> <p>Competence Centres clearly indicated the key values that would have to be carried over from the Skills4EOSC project.</p> <p>The discussion also provided the update to the proposed governance and organisation structure of the CC Network. The information about the</p>

		event is available at: https://www.skills4eosc.eu/participate/events/workshop-making-the-competence-centres-network-sustainable-and-enhanced .
3	Skills4EOSC Competence Centre workshop 06 - 02 - 2025	<p>The first workshop of Skills4EOSC Competence Centres was focused on number of topics extending well beyond the end of the project.</p> <p>The key concepts of sustainability and governance of CC Network were presented based on input from the Berlin workshop.</p> <p>Competence Centres have in general accepted the approach and agreed to establish the CC Network as a vehicle to carry over the outcomes of the project after its end.</p> <p>Competence Centres also provided guidance towards further finalisation of procedures to establish CC Network for continuation beyond the duration of the project.</p>
4	Skills4EOSC Competence Centre workshop 28 - 05 - 2025	<p>The main topic of this workshop was the preparation for establishment of CC Network.</p> <p>Competence Centres have adopted the governance procedures including the ascension procedures, role of the General Assembly and Editorial Board.</p> <p>Competence Centres have agreed with the roadmap of further actions.</p>
5	Skills4EOSC Paris workshop and final 10-11 06 2025	The workshop primarily addressed short- and long-term evolution perspectives and priorities.

project event		<p>The presentations by partners from EOOSC governance and European Commission has helped to provide more clarity on potential paths of integration with the federation of EOOSC Nodes.</p> <p>Participants of workshop provided clear guidance on the value and importance of tangible outputs of the project as well as more general outcomes like advocacy and representation.</p> <p>The results of the active sessions of the workshop are presented in the Appendix 1. These results are represented in the proposed roadmap for sustainability in chapter 5 of this document.</p>
6	1 st meeting of CC Network General Assembly 24 - 07 - 2025	<p>The 1st meeting of CC Network GA has established it as an independent community with the light-weight formal governance scaffolding to sustain and evolve outcomes of Skills4EOOSC project.</p> <p>GA has adopted the organisation structure and initial rules of order.</p> <p>GA has appointed the presiding Competence Centre and the chairman of the GA.</p> <p>Presiding Competence Centre provided the information on infrastructure resource availability.</p> <p>GA also endorsed the proposed structure of the roadmap towards long-term sustainability.</p>